

SAJPCI

Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues (SAJPCI)

Editor-In-Chief

Dr. B.E. Agesin

Managing Editors

Dr A.O. Olaseni

Dr. D.A. Fagbenro

Associate Editors:

Mr O. A. Popoola

Dr. (Mrs) S.I. Alliu

Published by:

Department of Psychology,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

www.fssunilorinedu.org/sajpci

Editor-In-Chief

Dr. B.E. Agesin

Associate Editors

Mr O. A. Popoola

Dr. (Mrs) S.I. Alliu

Managing Editors

Dr A.O. Olaseni

Dr. D.A. Fagbenro

Editorial Advisory Board

Dr. J. O. Oyeleke – Leadcity University, Ibadan

Professor B.O. Ehigie – Department Psychology, University of Ibadan

Professor A. O. Sunmola – Department Psychology, University of Ibadan

Professor J. A. Ogunleye – Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti

Professor E. Ihaji – Reverend Father Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi

Professor O. A. Ojedokun – Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko,
Nigeria

Professor E.S. Idemudia – Faculty of the Humanities, North-West University,
Mafikeng, South Africa

Professor S. O. Adebayo – Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti.

Professor I. E. Onyishi – University of Nigeria, Nsukka

Dr. M. A. Tafida – Nasarawa State University, Keffi

Professor B.O. Omolayo – Federal University Oye-Ekiti

Published by

Department of Psychology

Faculty of Social Sciences

University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

www.fssunilorinedu.org/sajpci

GUIDELINES FOR CONTRIBUTORS

Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues (SAJPCI) is a publication of the Department of Psychology, Faculty of the Social Sciences, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. It uses a psychological approach to handle issues of development in Africa. Articles for publication which may be from the field of Social Sciences or any other related field are expected to have particular relevance to African culture, ideas and developments.

Manuscripts should be submitted through the dedicated email (psychology@unilorin.edu.ng) using Microsoft word, Times New Roman Font size 12 with double line spacing. The APA (7th Edition) references style should be adopted and article with reference should not exceed 6000 words.

The Editor-in-Chief

Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues (SAJPCI)
Department of Psychology
Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria
P.M.B. 1515, Ilorin, Nigeria.

SAJPCI
Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and
Contemporary Issues

Vol. 2, No. 1. March, 2026

ISSN: 2805-380X

A Publication of
Department of Psychology
Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

Content	Pages
Hopelessness and Emotional Vulnerability as Drivers of Cannabis Use Disorder among Young Adults in Nigeria Judith C. AZIKWE, Olugbenga D. DADA, Sikirulai A. SULAIMAN, Yemi AKEREDOLU & Ayodeji M. BALOGUN	1-11
Examining the Nexus among Occupational Hazards, Gender and Psychological Wellbeing among Selected Healthcare Workers in Ilorin Metropolis, Nigeria Paul O. AJAO, Sikirulai A. SULAIMAN & Omosolape O. OWOSEN	12-29
Navigating Retirement without a Safety Net: Exploring Household size, Marital status, Family Structure and Religion as Predictors of Retirement Planning Behaviour among Older self-employed in Ilorin Blessing O. OREDOLA, Dare A. FAGBENRO, Zainab M. AZEEZ & Oladimeji O. OMOJOLA	30-49
Work Stress and Coping Strategies among Staff of University of Ilorin Health Service Unit, Ilorin, Nigeria: A Qualitative Study Abdullateef Abiodun ATIKU, Akangbe Tomisin ADEDUNMOLA & Olubukola AJAYI	50-67
Health Seeking Behaviour and Health Locus of Control as Predictors of Cyberchondria among the Elderly Residents in Ekiti State Olubukola AJAYI & Abiodun Atiku ABDULATEEF	68-80
Mediating Role of Drug Use History in the Relationship Between Clinical Personality Patterns and Criminal Behaviour Oladimeji O. OMOJOLA, Abayomi O. OLASENI, Blessing O. OREDOLA & Zainab M. AZEEZ	81-97
Influence of Age and Gender on Body Shaming Behaviour among Adolescents and Young Adults in Ilorin Zainab M. AZEEZ, Abiola O. POPOOLA, Blessing O. OREDOLA & Oladimeji O. OMOJOLA	98-114
Death Anxiety, Religiosity, and Meaning in Life as Predictors of Relapse among Psychiatric Patients in selected Neuro-Psychiatric Hospitals in Southwest Nigeria Adekunle Yemi AKEREDOLU, Adedeji Julius OGUNLEYE, Olugbenga David DADA & Busayo Mary ADEKOLA	115-133
Religious Intolerance as a Predictor of Violent Behaviour Tendency among Ilorin Residents, Kwara State, Nigeria Omoniyi S. AJAYI & Abayomi O. OLASENI	134-147
Illness Representation, Coping, Emotional Regulation, and Adaptation in Hereditary Hemorrhoidal Illness (Jẹ̀dìjẹ̀dì) among Yoruba Nigerians Sadiat Iyabode ALLIU, Dare Azeez FAGBENRO, Bamikole Emmanuel AGESIN, Stephen Ishola BABATUNDE, Leonard Chidozie ORJI & OluFolakemi Victoria ADEDEJI	148-175
Exploring the Role of Social Media on Psychological Well-Being, Cultural Identity, Civic Engagement, and Governance among Nigerian Youths: A Qualitative Study Leonard C. ORJI, Sadiat I. ALLIU, Ajibola A. ISHOLA & Moses T. IMBUR	176-199
Untangling the Mind Behind Bars: How Emotion Regulation Connects Self-Efficacy, Guilt-Induced Depression, and Suicidal Ideation in Ilorin Correctional Facility Bamikole Emmanuel AGESIN & Oluwatoyin ADENIRAN	200-218
Job characteristics, and the Influence of Gender and Educational Qualification on Marital Satisfaction of Married Working Individuals Helen Foluke OLAGUNDOYE	219-230
From Offline Isolation to Online Escape: Psychosocial Pathways to Digital Refuge-Seeking Behaviours among Adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria Vitoria O. AKPAN, Ezekiel O. ARUOTURE, Femi E. BABALOLA & Shyngle K. BALOGUN	231-255

Article History

Received Date: 25 November /2025

Revised: 02 February 2026

Accepted Date: 06 February 2026

Published Date: 31 March 2026

**Influence of Age and Gender on Body Shaming Behaviour among Adolescents and
Young Adults in Ilorin**

Zainab M. AZEEZ, Abiola O. POPOOLA, Blessing O. OREDOLA

& Oladimeji O. OMOJOLA

Department of Psychology, University of Ilorin, Nigeria

Correspondence: zainabazeezmorayo@gmail.com, Orcid: 0009-0004-0922-5991

Abstract

Body-shaming behaviours have become increasingly rampant among young people, particularly in communities where societal expectations and media influences shape perceptions of appearance. This study examined the influence of age and gender on body-shaming behaviours among adolescents and young adults in Ilorin. A descriptive survey approach was employed, and information was obtained from 300 adolescents and young adults aged 13– 28 years using the body esteem scale questionnaires measuring experience in body-shaming. Data analysis was conducted using quantitative method, specifically one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to examine age differences and an independent sample t-test to assess gender differences. The results revealed a statistically significant difference in body shaming behaviour across age groups, $F(3, 287) = 4.70, p = <.05$. Additionally, a significant gender difference was observed, with males reporting higher body shaming scores than females ($t(289) = 2.02, p <.05$). These findings suggest that body shaming experiences vary across developmental stages and are influenced by gender.

Keywords: Adolescents, Age, Body shaming, Gender, Young adults, Ilorin.

Introduction

Body shaming (BS) has become a pervasive social and psychological issue that exceeds culture, geography, and age boundaries. It refers to behaviours that mock, criticize, tease, or humiliate individuals based on their physical characteristics, including body size, shape, and appearance. (Gam et al., 2020). According to Ragelienė (2019), young people are especially susceptible to psychological and social issues including body shaming. Among young adults, such behaviors are progressively more visible both offline and online, reflecting entrenched societal pressures surrounding physical appearance (Deviantony et al., 2024). Body-shaming behaviour have become increasingly common among young people across various cultural settings, including Nigeria. Body-shaming behaviors can occur through ridiculing, taunting, verbal derision, disparaging remarks, or online harassment, and are frequently linked to adverse mental health consequences, such as anxiety, diminished self-esteem, and depression (Czeczor-Bernat et al., 2023; Novotný et al., 2025).

In Nigeria, body image dissatisfaction is widespread among young people, with studies indicating a significant occurrence of this issue among undergraduates (Olatona et al., 2023). Cultural and media-driven beauty standards, including Western-influenced ideals, have been identified as contributors to body shaming and negative self-esteem in Nigerian university settings (IJBP, 2025). Svindseth and Crawford (2019) demonstrated that humiliation can arise from an individual's failure to conform to societal expectations of identity. They contend that persons who don't match the coping mechanisms of the lifestyle that society values are more likely to be humiliated. According to a far earlier study by Shwartz et al. (2006), people in our culture would sooner lose a limb than gain weight. As social media amplifies exposure to idealized body images and peer evaluation, the risk of engaging in or being victimized by body-shaming behaviors continues to grow, especially within communities undergoing rapid modernization such as Ilorin, Kwara State.

Bullying someone because of their physical appearance is known as body shaming, and it can have a negative effect on a person's mental health. Body shaming, whether it comes from oneself or from others, can cause sadness, low self-esteem, concern about one's looks, and even suicidal thoughts (Mustafa et al., 2022). According to Chirayath and Premamalini (2024), perpetrators of body shaming may lack awareness of the impact their actions have on victims. Body shaming can have an impact on a person's mental health, social health, career, and personal life, even though it only pertains to physical appearance-based shame (Arumugam et al., 2022). Social appearance anxiety, melancholy, and low self-esteem can result from body

shaming, whether it occurs inwardly or externally (Ahmad & Safdar, 2025). According to a study by Syeda and Mumtaz (2023), body shaming episodes are common among young people and can have a significant negative impact on their social and mental health. According to a growing body of research highlighting the detrimental effects of appearance-based harassment among young people, body shaming frequently results in low self-esteem, low body dissatisfaction, and depressive symptoms (Gam et al., 2020).

One of the demographic factors that may influence how individuals engage in or experience body-shaming behaviors is age. Age is a critical developmental factor influencing how individuals perceive their bodies, interpret social pressures, and respond to appearance-based comments. Studies by Obi 2025; Vankerckhoven et al., 2025), shows that younger adolescents are more vulnerable to appearance-related criticism due to heightened sensitivity to peer evaluation and the identity-formation process. According to research, these behaviors frequently appear throughout adolescence, a developmental stage characterized by increased peer comparison and self-consciousness (Gam et al., 2020). A Moroccan study found that appearance-related avoidance behaviors increased with age, indicating that as adolescents grow older, they may become more reactive to appearance norms and more likely to engage in or respond to shaming dynamics (Anonymous et al., 2022). Similarly, Czepczor-Bernat et al. (2023) found that body-related shame can occur as early as ages 7 to 12, implying that body-shaming tendencies may evolve with age as individuals internalize sociocultural beauty standards. In online contexts, age differences have also been observed in the ways adolescents and young adults participate in or respond to body-shaming incidents (Novotný et al., 2025). According to a 2013 study conducted by the UK government, children as young as five were considered sad due to their appearance (Burrowes, 2013). According to Tomiyama (2014), body shaming can therefore happen at any point in a person's life. According to research, between 25 and 35 percent of people worldwide engage in body shaming (Gam et al., 2020). During puberty, adolescents are vulnerable to a variety of body-shaming scenarios (Chirayath & Premamalini, 2024).

A survey conducted by the Ministry of Communication and Information in 2019, involving 2,000 individuals aged 13 to 64 years, revealed that approximately 94% of female adolescents and 64% of male adolescents have experienced body shaming (Indonesia Baik, 2019). According to earlier research, body shaming causes symptoms of despair, suicidal thoughts, low self-esteem, and poor psychological health (Grabe et al., 2007). In a cross-sectional research of 800 school-age adolescents in Lucknow, India, Gam et al. (2020) found

that at least 44.9% of respondents had experienced body shaming at least once in the previous year, with males in coeducational schools experiencing the highest rate and girls' schools experiencing the lowest. According to Buchianeri et al. (2014) and Eisenberg et al. (2013), the prevalence of appearance-based problems was found to be 38.2% and 30%, respectively. These results indicate a higher prevalence of body shaming. According to Gam et al. (2020), there was little change in the total number of reports by gender. However, victims of body shaming claimed to have occasionally been victimized. Maintaining peer relationships on campus, which serve as a safeguard against body shamers, or having a much wider network of close friends can lessen this issue (Brewis and Bruening, 2018).

During the developmental stage of adolescence, when children go through physical changes and enter a maturing phase, gender has a significant role (Chirayath & Premamalini, 2024). According to a study by Gam and colleagues (2020), body shaming is more common among guys than girls and affects young people frequently. Additionally, the study discovered that fat kids were more likely than other pupils to face body shaming. Similarly, Tylka (2011) explains that men experience body shaming through different ideals than women not necessarily thinness, but muscularity and strength. When men fail to meet these masculine body ideals, they are shamed for being too thin, too fat, or not muscular enough. Body shaming in men is rising and often underreported, but significant due to social norms around masculinity. Sugiati (2019) discovered that female students at FISIP Airlangga University in Indonesia are more likely than male students to face body shaming. Jokes and mocking of their physical appearance were examples of body-shaming behaviors. This leads to diminished self-assurance and heightened anxiety regarding one's public image. According to a different study, body image and emotional expression are correlated, and there is no discernible gender difference in body image (Saxena et al., 2020). A study by Griffiths and Touyz (2015) highlighted that men are increasingly exposed to muscular body ideals online. Males who don't meet these ideals experience body dissatisfaction, social comparison, and shaming, often from peers. Males may be more likely than females to be body shamed by other males, especially in gym and peer settings. Supporting this, McCabe and Stanford (2002) found that males reported high levels of body dissatisfaction, especially related to muscularity and height. These concerns led to greater experiences of body shaming, particularly in male-dominated environments like sports. Male body shaming was prevalent than previously assumed, and driven by different appearance standards. Youth body shaming, particularly in adolescence, causes low self-esteem and unpleasant attitudes, sometimes even suicidal ones. It is challenging to deal with the perception

that others don't like one's looks, which frequently sparks conversation among others (Chirayath & Premamalini, 2024). In line with a study by McCabe and Ricciardelli (2004) provided evidence that boys often experience shaming for not having “masculine” bodies, including being ridiculed for being skinny, fats or not athletic. Body shaming is common among adolescent boys and has been increasing due to muscularity pressures. Four teenage girls' experiences of body shaming were investigated from a qualitative perspective in a study conducted in Indonesia by Fauzia et al. (2019) utilizing the Theory of Socialized Anxiety and Theory of Social Phenomenology. According to the study's findings, body shaming has been prevalent among participants since middle school and is typically carried out by their peers. According to WCNC Charlotte (2017), a survey revealed that 64% of teenage boys and 94% of all teenage girls had experienced body shame. Given that everyone, regardless of age, has easy access to the internet and is constantly reminded of moral principles and what constitutes appropriate behavior, this is undoubtedly a startling truth.

Theoretically, (SCT) social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954) gives valuable insight in understanding body shaming behaviours among youths. It describes how people assess their own beliefs and aspirations by contrasting them with those of others. It is the notion that people are motivated to assess their own beliefs and skills by looking at external representations. Young individuals are more likely to make frequent and emotionally charged appearance comparisons due to heightened sensitivity to peer evaluation. This comparison may result in negative self-perception, body dissatisfaction, and the reinforcing of body-shaming behaviors. According to research by Myers & Crowther (2009), women who frequently compare themselves to others have lower self-esteem and more body dissatisfaction, which can lead to self-shaming behaviors. Festinger suggested that humans use social comparison to evaluate their skills and value. People who engage in body shaming compare their bodies to unrealistic beauty standards and idealized pictures found in the media, among their peers, or in social organizations. A framework for comprehending how body shaming results from comparing oneself to idealized body representations is provided by social comparison theory. Upward comparisons have been repeatedly linked to public humiliation, self-criticism, and body dissatisfaction. There are also gender differences: men compare based on physical strength or muscularity, whilst women are more likely to compare based on attractiveness. Therefore, how young people participate in or are impacted by body-shaming behaviors is significantly influenced by their age and gender.

Despite the fact that body shaming is widely acknowledged, little study has been done on how age and gender predict body-shaming behaviors among young Nigerians. The majority of previous research by Day et al., (2022); Schittenhelm et al., (2025), has focused on victimization, body image, and self-esteem; the socio-demographic component of body shaming - that is, how people deliberately participate in such behaviors has received less attention. By investigating the degree to which age and gender influence body-shaming behaviors among young people in Ilorin, this study aims to close this gap and advance knowledge of appearance-related behavioral inclinations within the Nigerian sociocultural setting.

Objective of the study

1. Determine whether body shaming behaviour differs across age groups among adolescents and young adults.
2. Examine the extent to which body shaming behaviour occur between male and female adolescents and young adults.

Research hypotheses

H1: There will be a significant difference in body shaming behaviour across age groups among adolescents and young adults.

H2: There will be a significant gender difference in regards to body shaming among adolescents and young adults.

Methods

Research Approach

This study employs quantitative research, which is a methodical approach that tests objective ideas by utilizing statistical methods to look at the links between quantifiable variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). It emphasizes impartiality, accuracy, and generalizability and is based on numerical data gathered via organized instruments (Apuke, 2017). This method works well for the current study because body-shaming behaviors, age, and gender can all be measured, and the study's goal is to utilize ANOVA to ascertain the influence of these variables.

Research Design

The cross-sectional survey approach used in this study is an observational, non-experimental research technique that collects data from participants all at once (Setia, 2016). Without

changing any factors, this design enables the researcher to take a "snapshot" of connections (Pubrica, 2025; NCBI, 2024).

Instruments

Section A: Socio-demographic information

This section includes a two-item scale, which seek information on the respondents' personal information. This includes age and gender.

SECTION B: Body esteem scale (BES)

Body Esteem Scale (BES) was created by Mendelson et al. (2001) to assess body esteem which refers to self-evaluating feelings related to one's body and appearance. It specifically measures three dimensions which are: Appearance, Weight and Attribution. This scale is applicable to both adolescents and adults and provides a comprehensive view of body image beyond superficial appearance satisfaction. Each of the 23 items on the measure is graded on a 5-point Likert scale that ranges from "never" (0), "seldom" (1), "sometimes" (2), "often" (3), to "always" (4). Positive body esteem is indicated by higher scores, whereas negative body image or body dissatisfaction is indicated by lower scores. The scale has questions like "I like what I look like in pictures", "I am satisfied with my weight", "Other people consider me good looking" and so on. Some items like (7, 9, 11, 13, 17, 21, 4, 18, and 19) are negatively worded and require reverse scoring before calculating total or subscale scores. Subscales scores are computed by summing or averaging item responses. The scale exhibits strong construct convergent validity. It has been shown to correlate in expected directions with other psychological measures such as self-esteem and depression. Cronbach's alpha values for the three subscales of BES range from 0.81 to 0.94, indicating strong internal consistency. The Cronbach's alpha value for this study was 0.98.

Inclusion Criteria

To be eligible for the study, participants must fulfill each of the following requirements: Participants must be at least 13 years old; Only individuals living within Ilorin was included to maintain geographical focus; Participants needed sufficient English proficiency to understand and respond to the questionnaire accurately and participants only was included if they actively agreed to participate and complete the online consent form.

Exclusion Criteria

Participants were not allowed to continue with the study if they: Participants who are below 13 years of age; participant that does not reside in Ilorin, Kwara State. To avoid geographical inconsistencies in the data; Participants who are unable to comprehend English. Misunderstanding the questionnaire could lead to inaccurate responses; participation must be fully voluntary; unwilling individuals will not be included.

Sampling techniques

The study made use of three hundred (300) respondents for this study. The study employed convenience sampling method, in which the researcher selects participants who are easiest to access or reach. These are individuals who are readily available and willing to take part in the study without random selection. Because participants are chosen based on their availability and willingness to participate, it is the simplest sampling technique. Without requiring a complete population list, convenience sampling enables researchers to readily access students or young people in schools, universities, churches, and mosques.

Procedure and method of data analysis

The questionnaires were distributed online through social media (such as Facebook, whatsapp, telegram and so on). The significance of the study as well as its goals and/or purpose were explained to the participants. Additionally, instructions on how to fill out the questionnaires were provided, and participants were urged to answer as honestly as possible. The participants were reassured by the researcher that no personal information would be included in their questionnaires. Participants complete the questionnaires on their mobile phones or computers at their convenience. The youth population will be separated into subgroups (e.g., age, gender) using convenience sampling. After that, participants will be chosen at random from each grouping. The questionnaire will include an informed consent form that highlights voluntary involvement, guarantees anonymity, and explains the goal of the study. Two hundred and ninety-one (291) of the three hundred (300) questionnaires that were distributed were retrieved, nine of which rejected consent, resulting in a 96.7% response rate. The internet platform (such as Google Forms) was used to automatically gather responses. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 was used to do the necessary statistical analysis on the completed questionnaires.

Ethical consideration

The institutions' departmental ethics committees gave their previous ethical approval for this investigation. Based on informed consent, participation in the study was entirely optional, and participants could opt out at any time without facing any repercussions. For participants below age 18 years, informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardian, while assent was obtained from the adolescents themselves before participation. By gathering no personally identifiable information from the respondents and securely keeping the data so that only the researcher could access it, anonymity and confidentiality were rigorously upheld.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There will be a significant difference in body shaming behaviour across age groups among adolescents and young adults. The hypothesis was tested using one-way ANOVA and the result presented on Table 1.

Table 1: One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) showing the influence of age on body shaming behavior among adolescents and young adults

	SS	Df	M S	F	Sig
Between Groups	13,194.35	3	4,398.12	4.70	.003
Within Groups	268,558.14	287	935.74		
Total	281,752.49	290			

The table presented above revealed that there is a significant influence of age on body shaming $F(3,287) = 4.70, p < .05$). This explained that body shaming is not experienced uniformly across different ages. Therefore, the hypothesis is hereby accepted.

Table 2: Showing the post-hoc analysis

Variables	X	SD	1	2	3	4
Group 1	0.33	0.58	—	—	—	—
Group 2	60.10	27.64	59.76*	—	—	—
Group 3	51.39	30.55	51.05*	8.71	—	—
Group 4	48.20	33.31	47.87	11.89	3.19	—

Group 1=13 – 16, Group 2= 17 – 20, Group 3= 21 – 24, Group 4= 25-28

The post-hoc analysis in table 2 indicate that respondent in group 2 (M= 60.10, SD= 27.64, $p < .01$) scored the highest on body shaming compared to respondent in group 3 (21-24M= 51.39, SD= 30.55, $p < .01$). This explained that body shaming experiences vary across different

age. It revealed that **participants aged 13–16 differed significantly from those aged 17–20 and 21–24**. This implies that **early adolescents experience body shaming more compared to older adolescents and young adults**.

Hypothesis 2: There will be significant gender difference on body shaming behaviour. The hypothesis was tested using t-test for independent measure and the result presented on Table 3

Table 3: Summary table showing analysis of Independent Sample of t-test of gender on body shaming

DV	Gender	N	Mean	Std	df	t	P
Body shaming	Male	97	54.54	26.32	289	2.02	<.05
	Female	194	50.60	33.32			

The Table above revealed that there is a significant influence of gender difference on body shaming (289) =2.02, $p < .05$). This means that male respondents with (Mean = 54.54; SD = 26.32) have the same score higher than their female counterparts (Mean = 50.60; SD = 33.32) on body shaming. This indicates a significant difference between males and females. The result further emphasizes that body shaming is higher among males than females. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion

This study examines the influence of age and gender on body shaming behavior among adolescents and young adults in Ilorin. This study proposes two hypotheses based on the objectives of the study.

The first hypothesis, which stated that there will be a significant difference in body shaming behaviour across age groups among adolescents and young adults in Ilorin, was confirmed and accepted. The one-way ANOVA results showed a statistically significant difference in body shaming behaviour across age groups. This finding suggests that body shaming is not experiences uniformly across different ages, supporting the notion that developmental stage plays an important role in how individuals perceive and experience body-related stigma. This goes in line with *Emilie Lacroix and colleagues (2023) which found that body image concerns change from early adolescence through age 24, noting that girls' body image tends to worsen before improving, and that changes are age-related*. A study by *Van den Berg et al. (2010) reported that age is one of the key factors affecting levels of body dissatisfaction and related constructs in adolescence*. Post hoc analyses further clarified this difference, indicating that participants aged 13–16 differed significantly from those aged 17–20 and 21–24. This implies

that early adolescents experience body shaming more compared to older adolescents and young adults. One possible explanation is that early adolescence is a critical developmental period marked by rapid physical changes, heightened self-consciousness, and increased sensitivity to peer evaluation. These factors may make younger adolescents more vulnerable to body-related comments and negative social comparisons. The absence of significant differences among some of the older age groups suggests that as individuals progress into late adolescence and young adulthood, body shaming experiences may stabilize or become more similar, possibly due to improved coping skills, greater body acceptance, or increased autonomy from peer influence.

The second hypothesis, which stated that there will be a significant gender difference in regards to body shaming among the adolescents and young adults in Ilorin, was confirmed and accepted. According to a study by Gam and colleagues (2020), body shaming is more common among guys than girls and affects young people frequently. Another finding by Griffiths and Touyz (2015) highlighted that men are increasingly exposed to muscular body ideals online. Males who don't meet these ideals experience body dissatisfaction, social comparison, and shaming, often from peers. Males may be more likely than females to be body shamed by other males, especially in gym and peer settings. Similarly, Tylka (2011) explains that men experience body shaming through different ideals than women not necessarily thinness, but muscularity and strength. When men fail to meet these masculine body ideals, they are shamed for being too thin, too fat, or not muscular enough. Body shaming in men is rising and often underreported, but significant due to social norms around masculinity. Supporting this, McCabe and Stanford (2002) found that males reported high levels of body dissatisfaction, especially related to muscularity and height. These concerns led to greater experiences of body shaming, particularly in male-dominated environments like sports. Male body shaming was prevalent than previously assumed, and driven by different appearance standards. In line with a study by McCabe and Ricciardelli (2004) provided evidence that boys often experience shaming for not having "masculine" bodies, including being ridiculed for being skinny, fats or not athletic. Body shaming is common among adolescent boys and has been increasing due to muscularity pressures.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of age and gender on body shaming behavior among adolescents and young adults in Ilorin. The findings demonstrated that both age and gender significantly influenced body shaming behavior, indicating that body shaming experiences vary across developmental stages and between males and females.

The significant age differences revealed that body shaming is particularly salient during adolescence, with early adolescents differing significantly from older adolescents and young adults. This highlights adolescence as a critical developmental period during which individuals may be more vulnerable to body-related criticism and negative social evaluation. As individuals transition into young adulthood, body shaming experiences appear to become more stable, possibly due to increased psychological maturity and improved coping mechanisms. Gender also demonstrated a significant influence, indicating that male and female youths experience and interpret body shaming differently due to societal and cultural expectations surrounding physical appearance. While we all think body shaming behaviors are more common in female than male. Several studies highlighted that men are increasingly exposed to muscular body ideals online. Males who don't meet these ideals experience body dissatisfaction, social comparison, and shaming, often from peers.

Overall, the results emphasize the necessity of age- and gender-specific treatments that support good body image and lessen bullying of young people based on appearance. Mental health programs, school-based interventions, and public awareness campaigns should adopt inclusive approaches that address the unique experiences of adolescents and young adults, as well as males and females. Future studies should take into account qualitative methods to investigate individual accounts of body-shaming events as well as longitudinal designs to determine causal linkages. By addressing these factors, stakeholders can contribute to healthier self-esteem development and improved psychosocial wellbeing among young people in Ilorin.

Recommendation

In light of the study's findings, it was recommended that;

- Schools should integrate comprehensive body-image programmes into their curriculum. These programmes should cover topics such as self-esteem, body positivity, the impact of media on self-perception, and managing peer pressure. Teachers should receive training on how to identify body-shaming behaviors and

intervene appropriately. Early education is especially crucial for younger adolescents, who are more vulnerable to appearance-related criticism.

- Counselors, school psychologists, and social workers should recognize that males and females experience and respond to body-shaming differently. Female adolescents may internalize body dissatisfaction more deeply, while males may underreport due to stigma. Therefore, support services should be tailored to address these gender-specific experiences—such as girls’ empowerment clubs and programmes that help boys navigate body expectations and masculinity norms.

Limitation of the study

Despite the relevance, a number of limitations should be noted in order to direct future investigations. First off, the study's cross-sectional methodology makes it more difficult to determine the causes of age, gender, and body-shaming behaviors. It is challenging to ascertain whether these variables directly affect behavioral changes throughout time because the results only show relationships at one particular moment in time. Second, the study used self-report questionnaires, which are susceptible to recollection errors or social desirability bias. Fear of being judged or misinterpreting the questions may cause participants to either over-report or under-report their experiences of body shaming. Third, the results may not be as applicable to young people in other parts of Nigeria or in diverse cultural contexts because the sample was restricted to adolescents and young adults in Ilorin. Cultural norms, media exposure, and socioeconomic disparities may all have an impact on body-shaming experiences; these factors were not thoroughly examined in this study.

Furthermore, the study only looked at age and gender as predictors; other pertinent variables including exposure to social media, peer interactions, familial environment, and cultural standards of attractiveness were not investigated. A more thorough knowledge of the factors influencing body-shaming behaviors may have been possible if these variables had been included. Lastly, the application of purely quantitative techniques offers a macro-level view of body shaming but creates a depth deficit. It limits the capacity to document rich individual stories and explores deeper psychological interpretations – such as shame internalization, coping mechanisms, and identity reformulation- which are critical for developing effective, empathetic interventions. A more comprehensive understanding of youngsters' experiences may have been obtained by including qualitative perspectives into the data.

References

- Ahmad, G., & Safdar, Z. S. (2025). Body Shaming and Body Dissatisfaction with Mediating Role of Social Appearance Anxiety among Women University Students with Below and Above Average Body Mass Index. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 40(2), 461-482.
- Apuke, O. D. (2017). Quantitative research methods: A synopsis approach. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(10), 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0040336>
- Arumugam, N., Manap, M. R., Mello, G. D., & Dharinee, S. (2022). Body shaming: Ramifications on an individual. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(4), 1067-1078.
- Brewis, A. A., & Bruening, M. (2018). Weight shame, social connection, and depressive symptoms in late adolescence. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(5), Article 891. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15050891>
- Bucchianeri, M. M., Eisenberg, M. E., & Neumark-Sztainer, D. (2014). Weightism, racism, classism, and sexism: Shared forms of harassment in adolescents. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 53(1), 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2012.12.010>
- Burrowes, N. (2013). *Body image and self-esteem among children: A UK government report*. Department for Education. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/body-image-and-self-esteem>
- Chirayath, G., & Premamalini, K. (2024). The impact of body shaming and its effect on mental well-being in youth. *ShodhKosh: Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*, 5(6), 3617–3623. <https://doi.org/10.29121/shodhkosh.v5.i6.2024.6449>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Czeczor-Bernat, K., Modrzejewska, J., Brytek-Matera, A., & Modrzejewska, A. (2023). Body shame in 7–12-year-old girls and boys: The role of parental attention to children’s appearance. *Sex Roles*, 89(1), 82–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-023-01385-7>
- Day, S., Bussey, K., Trompeter, N., & Mitchison, D. (2022). The impact of teasing and bullying victimization on disordered eating and body image disturbance among adolescents: a systematic review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 23(3), 985-1006.
- Deviantony, F., Fitria, Y., Rondhianto, R., & Pramesuari, N. K. T. (2024). An in-depth review of body shaming phenomenon among adolescents: Trigger factors, psychological impact, and prevention efforts. *South African Journal of Psychiatry*, 30(1), Article a2341. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajpsy.2024.v30i0.2341>
- Eisenberg, M. E., Neumark-Sztainer, D., & Story, M. (2013). Associations of weight-based teasing and emotional well-being among adolescents. *Archives of Pediatrics & Adolescent Medicine*, 161(8), 733–738. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.161.8.733>

- Festinger, L. (1954). *A theory of social comparison processes*. *Human Relations*, 7(2), 117–140. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872675400700202>
- Fauzia, T. F., & Rahmiaji, L. R. (2019). Memahami pengalaman body shaming pada remaja perempuan. *Interaksi Online*, 7(3), 238–248.
- Gam, R. T., Singh, S. K., Manar, M., Kar, S. K., & Gupta, A. (2020). Body shaming among school-going adolescents: Prevalence and predictors. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 7(4), 1324–1328. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20201075>
- Grabe, S., Hyde, J. S., & Lindberg, S. M. (2007). Body objectification and depression in adolescents: The role of gender, shame, and rumination. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 31(2), 164–175. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-6402.2007.00356.x>
- Griffiths, S., & Touyz, S. (2015). A systematic review of body image and disordered eating in males: Towards a male body image model. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 36, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2014.11.001>
- Indonesia Baik. (2019). Pernah alami body shaming? Berikut cara lapornya. *Indonesia Baik*. https://indonesiabaik.id/motion_grafis/pernah-alami-body-shaming-berikut-cara-lapornya
- International Journal of Bullying Prevention (2025). *Bullying, body shaming, and academic behavior among university students in Nigeria*.
- Lacroix, E., Bégin, C., Blanchette-Martin, N., & Corneau, L. (2023). *Trajectories of body image from early adolescence to young adulthood*. *Journal of Adolescence*, 95, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2023.01.004>
- Mendelson, B. J., Mendelson, M. J., & White, A. (2001). Body-esteem scale for adolescents and adults. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 76(1), 90–106. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327752JPA7601_6
- McCabe, M. P., & Stanford, R. (2002). Body image and body change techniques among adolescent boys and girls. *Adolescence*, 37(146), 113–125
- McCabe, M. P., & Ricciardelli, L. A. (2004). Body image dissatisfaction among males across the lifespan: A review of past literature. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 56(6), 675–685. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3999\(03\)00129-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3999(03)00129-6)
- Mustafa, M. S. A., Mahat, I. R., Shah, M. A. M. M., Ali, N. A. M., Mohideen, R. S., & Mahzan, S. (2022). The awareness of the impact of body shaming among youth. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(4), 1096–1110.
- Myers, T. A., & Crowther, J. H. (2009). Social comparison as a predictor of body dissatisfaction: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 118(4), 683–698. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016763>
- National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). (2024). Study designs. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK92775/>

- Novotný, J. S., Konečný, M., Havelková, M., & Králová, P. (2025). Exploring the negative consequences of online body shaming among teenagers. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*. Advance online publication.
- Obi, S. N. (2025). Positive Body Image and Identity Formation among Senior Secondary School Adolescents in Ibadan South-East Local Government Area, Oyo State. *INSIGHT: Jurnal Bimbingan Konseling*, 14(2), 45-56.
- Olatona, F. A., Aladelokun, F. F., Adisa, O. O., Ogunyemi, A. O., & Goodman, O. O. (2023). *Body image dissatisfaction, nutritional status and weight control strategies among university undergraduates in Lagos, Nigeria*. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 45, Article 112. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2023.45.112.27382>
- Pubrica. (2025). Cross-sectional study in research. <https://www.pubrica.com/cross-sectional-study>
- Ragelienė, T. (2016). Links of adolescents' identity development and relationships with peers: A systematic literature review. *Journal of the Canadian Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 25(2), 97–105.
- Saxena, S., Mathur, A., & Jain, S. (2020). Body shaming, emotional expressivity, and life orientation among young adults. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 7(9), 487–493.
- Schittenhelm, C., Kops, M., Moosburner, M., Fischer, S. M., & Wachs, S. (2025). Cybergrooming victimization among young people: A systematic review of prevalence rates, risk factors, and outcomes. *Adolescent Research Review*, 10(2), 169-200.
- Schwartz, M. B., Vartanian, L. R., Nosek, B. A., & Brownell, K. D. (2006). The influence of our own body weight on implicit and explicit anti-fat bias. *Obesity*, 14(3), 440-447. <https://doi.org/10.1038/oby.2006.58>
- Setia, M. S. (2016). Methodology series module 3: Cross-sectional studies. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*, 61(3), 261–264. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5154.182410>
- Simply Psychology. (2023). Cross-sectional study. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/cross-sectional-study.html>
- Sugiati, T. (2019). The influence of body shaming toward FISIP Airlangga University students' behaviour pattern. *Indonesian Journal of Social Sciences*, 11(2), 16–24.
- Svindseth, M. F., & Crawford, P. (2019). *Humiliation: Mental health and public shame*. Emerald Publishing.
- Syeda, H., Shah, I., Jan, U., & Mumtaz, S. (2023). Exploring the impact of body shaming and emotional reactivity on the self-esteem of young adults. *CARC Research in Social Sciences*, 2(3), 60–67.

- Tomiyama, A. J. (2014). Weight stigma is stressful: A review of evidence for the Cyclic Obesity/Weight-Based Stigma model. *Appetite*, 82, 8–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2014.06.108>
- Tylka, T. L. (2011). Positive psychology perspectives on body image. In T. F. Cash & L. Smolak (Eds.), *Body image: A handbook of science, practice, and prevention* (2nd ed., pp. 56–64). Guilford Press.
- Van den Berg, P. A., Paxton, S. J., Keery, H., Wall, M., Guo, J., & Neumark-Sztainer, D. (2010). Body dissatisfaction and body comparison with media images in males and females. *Body Image*, 7(3), 257–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bodyim.2010.04.003>
- Vankerckhoven, L., Claes, L., Raemen, L., Palmeroni, N., Eggermont, S., & Luyckx, K. (2025). Longitudinal associations among identity, internalization of appearance ideals, body image, and eating disorder symptoms in community adolescents and emerging adults: Adaptive and maladaptive pathways. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 54(2), 290-309.
- WCNC Charlotte. (2017, September 21). Study finds most teens have been shamed for their bodies. *WCNC Charlotte*. <https://www.wcnc.com/article/news/local/study-finds-most-teens-have-been-shamed-for-their-bodies/418929418>
- Zakaria, R., Amor, H., & Baali, A.(2022). Body image perceptions and avoidance behaviours among a Moroccan group of adolescents. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 15, 1321–1331. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35499239/>